

Experimental Demonstration of 291 Gb/s/λ DSCM-WDM Metro-access Networks Leveraging SOA-based OADM Nodes

Zhouyi Hu, Vincent van Vliet, María Freire-Hermelo, Shiyi Xia, Menno van den Hout, Chigo Okonkwo, and Nicola Calabretta

Department of Electrical Engineering, Eindhoven University of Technology, 5600 MB Eindhoven, Netherlands, zhouyihu@ieee.org

Abstract For the first time, we experimentally demonstrate SOA-based optical add/drop multiplexer (OADM) nodes for dynamic wavelength drop & add operations in high-speed coherent DSCM-WDM metro-access networks. Results show 291 Gb/s/λ net data rate coherent DSCM transmission with highly flexible switching, supporting up to 5 nodes. ©2024 The Author(s)

Introduction

Numerous emerging network applications, e.g., 5G/6G and virtual/augmented reality, fuel the exponential growth of global internet traffic. Therefore, wavelength division multiplexing (WDM) technology has attracted much attention to cope with this challenge, for instance, in metro-access networks [1]-[3]. Besides higher capacity, these networks, bridging the gap between high-capacity metro/aggregation networks and end-user access networks, must adapt to evolving demands for lower latency, greater reliability, and enhanced service flexibility. Although it could be implemented by expensive wavelength-selective switches and fast-tunable transceivers [4], it is not a suitable choice for some cost-sensitive scenarios. In our previous work, we have demonstrated a lossless fast reconfigurable optical add-drop multiplexer (OADM) node based on semiconductor optical amplifiers (SOAs) for low-cost and highly flexible metro-access networks [5], [6]. However, only low-speed intensity-modulated and direct-detection optical transmission and switching assessment have been investigated.

Meanwhile, coherent digital subcarrier multiplexing (DSCM) is a promising technique for implementing high-capacity and flexible point-to-multipoint (P2MP) optical networks [7], [8]. Although most current research studies revolve around the filterless architecture with passive splitters/combiners, as data traffic increases, it is not a spectrally efficient approach and can only adapt to limited traffic pattern types [9]. Therefore, an efficient network architecture leveraging both DSCM and low-cost OADM is worth studying.

In this work, we design and experimentally demonstrate a novel metro-access network architecture with improved reconfigurability and spectrum efficiency compared to the popular filterless DSCM P2MP architecture. We successfully verify the scalability (up to 5 nodes) and flexibility of the proposed architecture through a proof-of-concept experiment at an aggregate net data rate of 291 Gb/s/λ, which is the first time to the best of our knowledge.

Fig. 1: Architecture of (a) metro-access networks enabled by (b) SOA-based OADM nodes.

Network Architecture

Fig. 1(a) illustrates a typical network architecture consisting of a metro-aggregation network with several metro-access scenarios. Distinctively shaped like a horseshoe, the metro-access network can serve different environments, ranging from urban to rural areas. As shown in the figure, the designed SOA-based OADM nodes are responsible for communicating between the two metro hubs at both edges and distributing the traffic for various access applications, e.g., 5G and fiber-to-the-home, where the nodes are capable of adding/dropping and blocking/continuing each WDM channel independently.

Fig. 1(b) depicts the architecture of the SOA-based OADM employed in this work. We can see from the figure that the WDM signal coming from one Hub or preceding nodes is first demultiplexed by an arrayed waveguide grating (AWG), then divided into two parts for either dropping (to the aggregation node) or feeding into SOAs by an array of splitters. The SOAs at each OADM node act as gates to let pass (SOA turned on) or block (SOA turned off) each optical channel independently. Moreover, the optical channels that pass through

Fig. 2: Proof-of-concept experiment for demonstrating coherent DSCM-WDM metro-access networks.

Fig. 3: Average BER of the dropped signals as a function of the SOA driving current at the previous node (Insets: constellation diagrams at different settings).

the node can be amplified by the SOAs to compensate for the link loss. Therefore no additional in-line amplifiers, e.g., expensive erbium-doped fiber amplifiers (EDFAs), are required in the proposed network architecture. Meanwhile, the wavelengths blocked by SOAs can be reused by adding traffic via an array of combiners. After the add operation, different optical channels are then combined again by another AWG, and sent to another Hub or following nodes.

In this work, we propose using the coherent DSCM technique to provide variable capacity to each node, and add variable capacity to the network from each node. Meanwhile, the OADM allows the reusing of the WDM channels, further increasing its flexibility. Moreover, the SOAs employed in our architecture can be integrated into a photonic-integrated circuit with AWGs, and provide nanosecond-scale switching time. Therefore, the designed architecture is a potential solution for high-performance but relatively low-cost metro-access networks.

Experimental Setup and Results

Fig. 2 illustrates the experimental setup in this work. The DSCM signal was first generated using offline digital signal processing (DSP) with 4 sub-carriers modulated by 16-ary quadrature amplitude modulation (16-QAM) symbols at 10 GBaud each. After root-raised cosine pulse shaping with a roll-off factor of 0.01, the 4 subcarriers were combined digitally in the frequency domain,

Fig. 4: Spectra of (a) the single-wavelength signal and (b) the WDM signal dropped at different nodes.

leading to an aggregate line data rate of 320 Gb/s/λ (=10 GBaud × 4 SC × 4 bits × 2 pol) for dual-polarization (DP) coherent transmission. The digital signal was up-sampled and sent to a 100-GSa/s digital-to-analog converter (DAC) to drive two independent DP-IQ modulators which modulated odd and even WDM tones produced by two external cavity laser (ECL) arrays. Before the combination, a 200-m single-mode fiber (SMF) is used for decorrelation. After passing through a booster EDFA to compensate for the transmission loss, the amplified WDM signal was fed to a horseshoe network consisting of 5 nodes with SMF span links of 16.8 km, 6.4 km, 1 km, 3.2 km, and 12.9 km, respectively. After transmission, the dropped signal was detected by a standard coherent receiver setup as shown in Fig. 2, where an amplified spontaneous emission (ASE) noise source and variable optical attenuator (VOA) were used to vary the optical signal-to-noise ratio (OSNR) which was measured using an optical spectrum analyzer (OSA). After being captured by an 80-GSa/s real-time oscilloscope (RTO), the signal was finally sent for the receiver-side coherent DSCM DSP and performance evaluation.

Without loss of generality, we carried out two proof-of-concept experiments in this work: (1) only one wavelength (1555.75 nm), but up to 5 nodes for scalability investigation; (2) two wavelengths (1555.75 nm and 1557.35 nm, i.e., 200-GHz spacing) in a two-node WDM network to investigate add and drop operations and possible cross-talk. As shown in Fig. 3, we first optimized the settings of the SOAs used in our architecture. We can see that all bit error rate (BER) curves first decrease and then increase as the driving current increases. This is because there is a

Fig. 5: (a) Average BER versus OSNR for the signal dropped at each node in the single-wavelength network (Insets: constellations of different signals at ~25-dB OSNR). (b) Estimated SNR of different subcarriers of the DSCM signal dropped at each node (Inset: electrical spectra). (c) Average BER versus OSNR for dropped and added signals in the WDM network.

trade-off between SOA output power and nonlinearity. When the driving current is too low, the low signal power causes a high noise figure of the pre-amplifier. However, when the driving current further increases, the SOA-induced nonlinearity becomes a dominant factor degrading the signal performance as shown in the constellations in Fig. 3. We can also notice from the figure that after passing through 4 SOAs (i.e., dropped at Node 5), the accumulated ASE noise from the cascaded SOAs became the major channel impairment, leading to a BER floor.

With the optimal SOA driving current setting, we measured the optical spectra of the signals dropped at each node for both single-wavelength and WDM cases as shown in Fig. 4(a) and (b), respectively. For easier comparison, the spectra have been rescaled, indicating the OSNR reduction after passing through each node. Specifically, the maximum achievable OSNRs in the single-wavelength case at Nodes 1-5 are 33.2 dB, 31.2 dB, 30.6 dB, 27.5 dB, and 26.0 dB, respectively.

Fig. 5(a) presents the average BER over all 4 subcarriers as a function of OSNR at each node, where we can see that all curves can achieve a BER below the hard-decision forward error correction (HD-FEC) threshold of 4.7×10^{-3} [10]. Therefore, after considering the overhead from pilots (1/34) and HD-FEC (6.25% [10]), the net data rate is ~ 291 Gb/s/ λ , i.e., ~ 72.8 Gb/s per subcarrier. However, we can see that the maximum achievable OSNR (highlighted by green circles) is reduced when passing through more SOA-based OADM nodes due to their inherent ASE noise added to the signal. Moreover, even at the same OSNR, the BER performance still becomes worse when crossing more nodes, which can be attributed to the accumulated SOA-induced nonlinearity as we discussed earlier in Fig. 3. By fixing the OSNR at around 25 dB, in the insets of Fig. 5(a), we have presented the constellation diagrams of the signals at Node 1 and Node 5, respectively, also indicating the perturbative effects

of SOA nonlinearity. In this work, the OSNR penalty after passing through 4 more nodes is ~ 2.5 dB at the HD-FEC threshold.

Next, we have focused on the performance of each subcarrier of the coherent DSCM signal at the maximum OSNR as shown in Fig. 5(b), where the inset presents the electrical spectra measured at different positions. We can see from the figure that although SOA-based OADM nodes degrade the performance of all subcarriers, their rates are different, indicating the filtering effect of the Gaussian AWGs.

Fig. 5(c) reports the performance evaluation of the add/drop of two WDM channels in a two-node WDM network. As each SOA in the OADM switches/amplifies an individual channel, both channels show similar performance and have negligible differences from the single-wavelength case. The small BER difference can be attributed to the difference in performance of the SOAs and DP-IQ modulators that we used for the two channels. To verify its flexibility in reusing wavelength, we have also investigated the performance of the traffic dropped and then directly added at the same wavelength to the horseshoe network at Node 1 by blocking the wavelength channel fed to the SOA (turned off). We can see from Fig. 5(c) that the newly added signal shows similar performance as the dropped signal at the same node, thanks to the high on/off ratio (>40 dB) of the SOAs used in our architecture.

Conclusions

In this work, we have experimentally demonstrated the first coherent DSCM-WDM metro-access network with SOA-based OADM nodes. The proposed scheme has successfully supported 5 nodes at a net data rate of 291 Gb/s/ λ (72.8 Gb/s per subcarrier). WDM and dynamic add/drop operations have also been demonstrated, showing a negligible penalty. All results indicate the great potential of the proposed architecture for future high-speed, flexible, and low-cost coherent metro-access networks.

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